

Glass-Ceramic Foams and Reticulated Scaffolds by Sinter-Crystallization of a Hardystonite Glass

Hamada Elsayed^{1,2}, Acacio Rincon Romero¹, Martiniano Picicco³, Jozef Kraxner⁴, Dusan Galusek^{4,5}, Paolo Colombo,^{1,6} Enrico Bernardo^{1,*}

¹ *Department of Industrial Engineering, Università degli Studi di Padova, Padova, Italy*

² *Ceramics Department, National Research Centre, Cairo, Egypt*

³ *Centro de Tecnología de recursos Minerales y Cerámica (CETMIC), Gonnet (La Plata), Argentina*

⁴ *Department of Glass Processing, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia.*

⁵ *Joint glass centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChFT STU, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia*

⁶ *Department of Materials Science and Engineering, the Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA 16801, US*

Abstract

In the present investigation, we focused on a glass-based route to hardystonite ceramics, which represent one of the most promising classes of biomaterials, in the form of highly porous scaffolds. A glass corresponding to the stoichiometry of a hardystonite solid solution ($\text{Ca}_2\text{Zn}_{0.85}\text{Mg}_{0.15}\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$) was first synthesized and reduced in the form of fine powders ($<40\ \mu\text{m}$). Highly crystallized samples were obtained by sinter-crystallization, in air, at 1000-1200 °C, starting from highly porous green bodies (porosity $>70\ \text{vol}\%$), obtained by direct foaming or stereolithography of specifically formulated suspensions. More precisely, foams were obtained by intensive mechanical stirring (with the help of a surfactant) of suspensions undergoing gelation, in weakly alkaline aqueous solutions. Reticulated structures with complex non-stochastic geometry, on the other hand, were obtained by digital light processing of glass powders suspended in a photosensitive organic binder. The intensive crystallization caused an excellent retention of the shapes generated at room temperature. The uniform microstructures, all comprising quite dense struts, favored the mechanical properties (with crushing strength well exceeding 2 MPa, with open porosity above 65 vol%).

Keywords: Hardystonite bioceramics; glass-ceramics; sintering; foams; additive manufacturing; scaffolds

* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed: e-mail enrico.bernardo@unipd.it; fax +39 049 8275505

Introduction

The most advanced bioactive materials for bone tissue applications combine biocompatibility (absence of any cytotoxic effect), bioactivity (stimulation of new tissue formation) and biodegradability (progressive replacement of the implant by new tissue) [1,2]. Obviously, the materials for a temporary bone replacement must fulfil strict morphological requirements, particularly in terms of porosity (above 100 μm) and interconnections between adjacent pores [1,2]. These requirements are generally accomplished by porous bodies (i.e. scaffolds) with stochastic or non-stochastic porosity, such as foams and reticulated scaffolds, respectively [3,4,5].

Among most recently established biomaterials for bone tissue engineering applications, hardystonite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{ZnSi}_2\text{O}_7$, or $2\text{CaO}\cdot\text{ZnO}\cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$) ceramics represent one of the most interesting alternatives to bioglasses. In particular, hardystonite-based materials significantly stimulate osteogenic differentiation, cell proliferation and differentiation (mesenchymal stem cells and bone cells, such as osteoblast-like cells and osteoclasts) and expression of ALP, osteocalcin and collagen type I when in contact with HOB cells [6-8].

Most hardystonite-based ceramics reported in the literature were derived from a multistep ceramic process, according to which powders are first prepared, typically by the sol-gel method, and then sintered [9-11]. Highly porous bioceramics were fabricated, starting from ceramic powders, according to quite traditional methods, such as the impregnation of sacrificial polymeric sponges (replica method), before sintering [12]. Despite the good homogeneity, these cellular (trabecular) structures are not optimized in terms of mechanical properties, due to the presence of hollow struts (powders deposited around the struts of the polymer substrates densify, upon sintering, in the form of empty tubules).

Glasses have the potential for improving replica-derived cellular structures, since the struts can be nearly fully densified by viscous flow [13]. However, such a positive impact of viscous flow may have a significant drawback, consisting of the collapse of the trabecular structure. In other words, viscous flow is acceptable only when adequately controlled, e.g. by means of crystallization of glass powders. Glasses with optimized formulations may undergo an advantageous sinter-crystallization process, according to which struts are first densified and later stabilized and reinforced by the precipitation of crystals [13].

Sinter-crystallization is actually advantageous also for the possibility of achieving highly porous, open-celled glass-ceramics with no polymeric substrate and/or with complex shapes, according to gel casting technology or additive manufacturing. In the first case, Elsayed et al. [14] recently showed that aqueous suspensions of fine glass powders undergo progressive hardening by

formation of gels, at the surface of glass particles, as a consequence of weak alkali activation (introduction of NaOH, at low molarity). Highly porous foams may be obtained by simple mechanical stirring, with the help of a surfactant, at room temperature. The open-celled structure, in the green state, is later set without deformation by sinter-crystallization. In the second case, glass powders can be suspended in a photocurable liquid binder. The application of stereolithography allows for the formation of variously-shaped composite scaffolds, later fired in air (for debinding) and sinter-crystallized [15].

The present paper is devoted to the extension of the sinter-crystallization technologies to hardystonite glass-ceramics. The crystallization of glasses has been recently shown by Zreiqat and coworkers [16-18] as a suitable way to achieve hardystonite-based porous ceramics, also obtained by additive manufacturing, with dense struts. However, the tested glasses were not formulated according to the hardystonite stoichiometry, resulting in the precipitation of a secondary, biologically inert, crystalline phase (gahnite (ZnAl_2O_4)), due to the presence of Al_2O_3 . In our case, the formulation relied solely on the particular crystal structure of hardystonite (melilite crystal structure), consisting of Ca^{2+} ions sandwiched between $\text{Zn}(\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7)^{4-}$ sheets, leading to solid solutions by replacement of Ca^{2+} as well as by modifications in the sheets [19-24]. More precisely, we investigated a Mg-containing solid solution (Mg^{2+} , in tetrahedral coordination, replacing part of Zn^{2+} ions in the $\text{Zn}(\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7)^{4-}$ sheets), considering the potential of both Zn^{2+} and Mg^{2+} in improving the functionality of calcium silicates [25]. Sinter-crystallization was effective in yielding highly homogeneous porous ceramics, with an excellent retention of the shape generated at room temperature, and featuring quite dense struts, in turn favoring the mechanical properties.

Experimental procedure

a) Starting materials

The starting materials consisted of a glass based on the stoichiometry of Mg-doped hardystonite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{Zn}_{0.85}\text{Mg}_{0.15}\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$, Mg-Hst). The detailed chemical formulation is available in Tab.1.

The glass batch was prepared from analytical grade ($\geq 99\%$) oxides and carbonates (SiO_2 , CaCO_3 , MgO (Centralchem, Slovakia) and ZnO (AFT Bratislava, Slovakia)) and melted in Pt-10%Rh crucible in laboratory furnace with Superkanthal heating elements at $1500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour in ambient atmosphere; the heating rate was $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. In order to avoid any crystallization the molten material was subjected to intensive cooling, by pouring into deionized water. The procedure yielded

a homogeneous glass in the form of a frit. The absence of any annealing step caused the glass to break easily into fragments, later reduced into fine powders by dry ball milling and manual sieving.

Tab.1 – Chemical formulation of the glass used for producing hardystonite glass-ceramics.

Oxide	Mg-Hst glass, theoretical		Mg-Hst glass, EDS
	mol%	wt%	wt%
SiO ₂	40	39.07	38.00 ± 0.09
CaO	40	36.47	36.16 ± 0.53
ZnO	17	22.49	23.34 ± 0.10
MgO	3	1.97	2.33 ± 0.04

For the preparation of the Mg-Hst glass for SEM investigations, the glass powder with size < 1 mm were embedded in a transparent resin (TranOptic, Buehler, USA) and the sample with a diameter of 25 mm was ground and polished (EcoMet/AutoMet 300 Grinder-Polisher, Buehler, USA). The sample after polishing was placed in an ultrasonic bath. Before the microanalysis, the samples was dried in an oven at 40°C for 30 min. Then, the Mg-Hst glass was subjected to scanning electron microscopy (Jeol JFM 7600, Japan), equipped with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS, Oxford, UK), in order to verify the chemical composition. Before the EDS-microanalysis (acceleration voltage 10-15kV and working distance 15 mm), the sample was coated with a thin carbon layer (10 nm) in order to ensure the conductivity of the sample surface.

Mg-Hst glass was also investigated by powder X-ray diffractometry (Panalytical Empyrean, Malvern Panalytical B.V., Almelo, the Netherlands), to verify the amorphous nature of the product. Finally, the characteristic temperatures (transition temperature, T_g , and crystallization temperature, T_{cryst}) were evaluated by differential thermal analysis (Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC3+, Zurich, Switzerland) operating at 10 °C/min in static air, from room temperature up to 1200 °C.

b) Preparation of foams

The glass frit was milled and sieved, the fraction under 75 µm was added to a 2M NaOH (reagent grade, Sigma-Aldrich, Gillingham, UK) aqueous solution, for a solid loading of 65 wt%. The glass slurries were kept under low-speed mechanical stirring (500 rpm) for 3h, inducing partial dissolution and gelation. A pre-curing step of 20 min at 75 °C in sealed conditions was applied to the slurries to further promote the gelation and increase the viscosity. After that, the slurries were foamed by vigorous mechanical mixing (2000 rpm), for 5 min after the addition of 4 wt% Triton X-100

(polyoxyethylene octyl phenyl ether, Sigma-Aldrich, Gillingham, UK) and subsequently cast in several cylindrical moulds (20 mm diameter). The wet foams were later left at 40 °C for 24 h, in order to complete the gelation and complete hardening, before demoulding.

c) Preparation of reticulated scaffolds

Highly porous reticulated scaffolds were fabricated using DLP (digital light processing). Glass powders, in the particle size of <38 µm size range, were suspended in a commercially available photocurable acrylic polymer (Tripropylene Glycol Diacrylate, Robofactory, Italy), already containing a suitable photo-initiator and photo-absorber, with a solid load of 60 wt%, in analogy with previous experiences [15]. The suspension was printed using the visible light range between 400–500 nm using a Digital Light Processing (DLP) printer (3DLPrinter-HD 2.0, Robofactory, Italy). The 3D printed structures were cleaned in an ultrasonic bath with isopropanol for 3 min, to remove the uncured resin, and then were heat-treated using a heating rate of 1°C/min up to 550 °C with a holding time of 5h to decompose the photo-cured polymer.

d) Ceramization and characterization

A pre-treatment aimed at burning out the surfactant was applied to the foams at 350 °C for 1 h, with a heating rate of 5 °C/min. Then, the foamed samples were sintered by direct insertion in a heated box furnace at 1000, 1100 and 1200 °C, with a holding time of 1 hour.

3D printed scaffolds were fired at 1000-1200 °C for 1 h, with a heating rate of 5 °C/min. The cooling rate was fixed at 2 °C/min.

The crystalline phase identification was performed by means of X-ray diffraction on powder samples (XRD; Bruker AXS D8 Advance, Bruker, Germany), supported by data from PDF-2 database (ICDD-International Centre for Diffraction Data, Newtown Square, PA) and Match! program package (Crystal Impact GbR, Bonn, Germany). Fourier transform IR spectroscopy (FTIR, FTIR model 2000, Perkin Elmer Waltham, MA) measurements were made on the foams, in both green and ceramized form.

The density of the ceramic parts was determined geometrically and by weighing with an analytical balance. The apparent and true densities of the various samples were measured by means of a gas pycnometer (Micromeritics AccuPyc 1330, Norcross, GA), operating with He gas on samples in bulk (foam or 3D printed scaffold) and powder forms. Morphological and microstructural characterizations were performed by optical stereomicroscopy (AxioCam ERc 5s Microscope

Camera, Carl Zeiss Microscopy, Thornwood, New York, USA) and scanning electron microscopy (FEI Quanta 200 ESEM, Eindhoven, The Netherlands).

The compressive strength of the porous ceramics was measured at room temperature, by means of an Instron 1121 UTM (Instron Danvers, MA) operating with a cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min. Each data point represents the average value of at least 10 individual tests.

Results and Discussion

The first investigations concerned the nature of the starting material. Fig.1 shows that Mg-Hst glass fragments (embedded in epoxy resin) did not exhibit any compositional gradient (that would be shown by an inhomogeneous grey tone in the backscattered electrons image of Fig.1a) or crystallization (Fig.1b corresponds to a X-ray amorphous material). Energy dispersive spectroscopy determinations (performed on several zones, marked by boxes in Fig.1a) revealed only minor deviations from the theoretical chemical composition, as reported in Tab.1.

Fig. 1. a) Mg-Hst glass fragments embedded in epoxy resin, for SEM-EDS analysis; b) X-ray diffraction pattern of as-synthesized Mg-Hst glass

Fig. 2. Morphology of Mg-HSt glass-ceramic foams: a) after activation and drying; b) after firing at 1100 °C; c,d) after firing at 1200 °C

Mg-Hst glass suspensions in alkaline aqueous solution were successfully foamed by intensive mechanical stirring, as illustrated by Fig.2a. The low-temperature hardening may be attributed to the formation, after alkali activation, of hydrated compounds, which could be detected by means of infrared spectroscopy (Fig.3) and X-ray diffraction (Fig.4) analysis. The starting glass presents a broad absorption band between $700\text{--}1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$, attributed to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibration of the O-Si-O groups in the SiO_4 tetrahedron. After alkali activation, this band appears slightly widened indicating a lower degree of order in the glass structure. However, most significant changes in the infrared spectrum for the activated glass arise from the presence of some new bands, consistent with the formation of silicate and carbonate hydrated compounds.

Compared to the low-temperature foaming of other glasses [14, 26], the band associated with the O-H stretching of calcium silicate hydrated compounds (wavenumber range of $3000\text{--}3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is less significant; on the contrary, the C-O stretching vibration related to the presence of carbonate

compounds (band centered at about 1400 cm^{-1}) is more intense. An additional band between $2800\text{--}2900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is associated to the C-H stretching vibrations of the surfactant. All these bands disappear after heat treatment indicating the decomposition of the associated species upon firing; in addition, the broad band between $700\text{--}1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ splits into narrower bands centered at $830, 910, 970$ and 1100 cm^{-1} , consistent with the formation of crystalline hardystonite [27], together with the peak located at $\sim 600\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Fig. 3. FTIR analysis of glass before and after the alkali activation

The diffraction patterns in Fig.4 clearly show that the alkali activation caused the formation of sodium carbonate hydrate (thermonatrite, $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, PDF#08-0448), that could be interpreted as the main phase responsible for low temperature hardening. The formation of other compounds is not clear, but we can observe a modification of the amorphous halo of the starting glass in the 2θ range of $\sim 30\text{--}32^\circ$. A crystal phase cannot be properly identified, but this 2θ range matches with the main diffraction peak of calcium silicate hydrate (tobermorite, $\text{Ca}_{2.25}(\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{7.5}(\text{OH})_{1.5}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, PDF#45-1480).

Fig. 4. Details on the effect of alkali activation by mineralogical analysis

Generally speaking, a narrow temperature gap between glass transition temperature (T_g) and crystallization temperature (T_{cryst}) is desirable in sinter-crystallization experiments, in order to achieve a good control of the shape of the manufactured body (imparted by means of any shaping technique) [15]. In fact, when firing at T_{cryst} or slightly above, the precipitation of crystal inclusions, in a pyroplastic mass of softened glass, is expected to freeze the viscous flow [15], so that the manufactured highly porous green structures have a homogeneous shrinkage but no significant collapse or coarsening.

Quite unexpectedly, for this specific glass, the alkali activation had a negative impact on the sintering/crystallization balance, when sintering at T_{cryst} . Glass particles did not virtually sinter at all, at the specific temperature (foams fired at 900 and 1000 °C collapsed under light pressure). Increasing the firing temperature to 1100 °C ($T_{\text{cryst}}+200$ °C) determined just a poor necking of adjacent glass particles (Fig.2b), producing still particularly brittle foams. Finally, sintered bodies with satisfactory strength could be achieved only at 1200 °C (see Fig.2c), far above T_{cryst} ($T_{\text{cryst}}+300$ °C).

The difficulty with sintering could be justified by the changes observed in the differential thermal analysis plots, shown in Fig.5. A well-defined exothermic peak corresponding to T_{cryst} was visible in the as received glass (in the form of fine powders). For the activated glass (fine powders first subjected to alkali activation and then dried), the crystallization peak was rather less intense, and

it was centered at a slightly lower temperature (~ 850 °C instead of ~ 860 °C). We can also note a slight reduction of the transition temperature (T_g). In our opinion, this could be justified by formation of a sodium-enriched glass layer, from the decomposition of gels formed at low temperature, around unreacted glass particles. This glass layer had a fluxing action (reducing T_g) and stimulated the crystallization, in analogy with previous findings [28]. In fact, despite being less intense than in the not-activated glass, the exothermic effect started just above the transition temperature (T_g).

Fig. 5. Differential thermal analysis curves of the as-prepared Mg-HSt fine powder (bottom plot) and after alkali activation (top plot)

The increase of firing temperature, up to 1200 °C, was thus necessary to stimulate the viscous flow. In any case, the obtained foams exhibited a good homogeneity and retained a significant open-celled porosity (Fig.2d). The characteristics of the obtained porosity are suitable for supporting vascularization, the bone ingrowth and the nutrient supply, suggesting that these components are good candidates for bone repairing [29,30].

The sintering at 1000-1200 °C led to nearly phase-pure materials. As shown in Fig.6a, most of the peaks were found to match those of pure hardystonite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{ZnSi}_2\text{O}_7$, PDF#72-1603). We can therefore posit that an effective inclusion of Mg^{2+} ions in the crystal phase was achieved, considering that the peaks of pure hardystonite practically overlap with those of the (Zn-free) Mg-based melilite,

known as Åkermanite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{MgSi}_2\text{O}_7$, PDF#83-1815). Only some minor peaks could not be attributed to melilite crystals.

Fig. 6. Mineralogical analysis of hardystonite-based glass-ceramic foams (“alk act”) and reticulated scaffolds (“DLP”): a) overview; b) detail of selected patterns

Sintering at 1000 °C ($T_{\text{cryst}}+100$ °C), if not satisfactory for foams formed by means of alkali activation, was adequate for reticulated scaffolds, manufactured by DLP (see Fig.7a-d). The firing (after the debinding stage at 500 °C that completely eliminated the crosslinked photopolymer) led to well sintered bodies, with no crack or geometric distortion. As expected, the crystallization was useful to retain the shape imparted by DLP (Fig.7a), except for a homogeneous shrinkage (40 vol%). Potentially efficient ‘freezing’ role of crystallization may be inferred from Fig.7b (detail of a sintered sample), clearly showing the stair-stepping effect typical of DLP, and corresponding to the overlapping of layers. Sintering determined the mutual joining of glass powders, but not a significant smoothing of the surface of the struts. The crystallization impeded any viscous collapse (many layers remained perfectly aligned, as shown by Fig.7c). The roughness is reputed to be favorable, from the perspective of bone tissue engineering, in promoting cell adhesion [31]. Moreover, the roughness is enhanced by many micro-sized pores (Fig.7d), at the struts surface.

The absence of alkali activation (favoring the crystallization) had a minor drawback in the phase purity of reticulated scaffolds, compared to foams. As shown by Fig.6b, the signals attributable

to other silicate phases were slightly stronger. The extra phases comprise zinc silicate (willemite, Zn_2SiO_4 , PDF#83-2270), calcium zinc silicate (petedunnite, $\text{CaZnSi}_2\text{O}_6$, PDF#40-0495), quartz (PDF#74-1811) and magnesium silicate (protoenstatite, MgSiO_3 , PDF#74-2017). The intensity of the peaks attributable to the latter Zn-free, Mg-containing phase is still so limited that we can consider it as just at minor traces level; Mg^{2+} ions most probably remained mostly in the hardystonite solid solution. In all cases, in foams as well as in scaffolds, the absence of any significant background in diffraction patterns suggests a high crystallization degree.

The presence of secondary phases is not considered to be a major issue, since all of them are present in biocompatible, bioactive and biodegradable bio-ceramics (except quartz, that is inert) [9,32,33,34]. In other words, by operating with a glass corresponding to the stoichiometry of hardystonite solid solution we maximized the content of biologically responsive crystal phases.

Fig. 7. Morphological details of reticulated hardystonite-based glass-ceramic scaffolds, before firing (a, top view) and after firing at 1000 °C (b, top view after firing; c, side view; d, surface)

Tab.2 reports the crushing strength of the developed hardystonite-based porous glass-ceramics. Samples from additive manufacturing are undoubtedly significant for their excellent strength, exceeding 6 MPa for a total porosity of 68 vol%. However, the foamed scaffolds also possessed a good crushing strength, especially considering their much higher porosity (77 vol%). The obtained values, moreover, compare well with those of hardystonite foams manufactured by means of more complicated processing (e.g. ceramization of foamed silicone resins, mixed with oxide fillers [35]) and also with the ranges reported by No et al. for doped bioactive calcium silicates [36].

The obtained strength/density value, for samples produced by additive manufacturing, may be seen as just a starting point. Considering the high flexibility of DLP, additional efforts will be carried out in the manufacturing of samples with alternative designs, specifically aimed at maximizing the mechanical properties (e.g. hexagonal architectures [17]).

Tab.2 - Physical and mechanical properties of the obtained cellular hardystonite-based glass-ceramics.

Cellular structure	Bulk density [g/cm ³]	True density [g/cm ³]	Total porosity [%]	Compressive strength [MPa]
Foam	0.75 ± 0.03	3.30 ± 0.02	78.0	2.6 ± 0.1
Reticulated scaffold	1.07 ± 0.04	3.35 ± 0.03	68.1	6.2 ± 0.3

Conclusions

The main findings of this study may be summarized as follows:

- The remarkable crystallization tendency of a glass corresponding to the stoichiometry of Mg-doped hardystonite may ‘freeze’ the viscous collapse, upon sintering, of highly porous bodies;
- Alkali activation is confirmed as a tool for the manufacturing of glass-ceramic foams by gel-casting; the setting of activated suspensions of hardystonite glass may be attributed to the formation of both silicate and carbonate hydrated phases;
- An alternative shaping option is provided by the setting of suspensions of hardystonite glass in photocurable acrylic resin, using DLP;
- The alkali activation modifies the balance between viscous flow sintering and crystallization, so that sintered porous bodies are achieved at 1200 °C. On the contrary, after the low temperature burn out of the photocurable binder, samples processed by DLP may be sinter-crystallized at just 1000 °C;

- For both processing options, the final glass-ceramic products feature hardystonite solid solution as main crystal phase, with limited traces of secondary phases. In addition, the developed porous samples all exhibit a good strength-to-density ratio.

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